

Degenerate Conditional Clauses for CDCL Hash Cryptanalysis

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Abstract. Standard CDCL solvers struggle on SHA-256 differential CNF instances, a gap traditionally addressed by Gaussian elimination. We identify a Boolean Constraint Propagation (BCP) blind spot in standard CNF encodings of the *Ch* and *Maj* nonlinear functions: when specific input differentials align, the output differential is logically forced, yet unit propagation cannot derive it without additional branching. We resolve this by introducing *degenerate conditional differential equivalence clauses*—short static redundant constraints (4 literals per bit for *Ch*, 6 for *Maj*) that make this determinism explicit at the CNF level, requiring no solver modifications. Our Docker-reproducible artifact yields 18-step free-start speedups of 30.72× on Kissat 4.0.4, 19.87× on CaDiCaL 3.0.0, and 8.84× on CryptoMiniSat 5.8.0, with 89–98% conflict reductions. Speedup scales with instance difficulty: the 20-step measured long-run achieves 29.2× (94% conflict reduction), while a harder 20-step family yields >135× lower bounds. White-box analysis shows BCP throughput rising 12–13% at 18 steps and nearly tripling at 20 steps as the BCP blind spot dominates. We also document that carry-chain clauses (5–6 literals) and Σ_0/Σ_1 clauses provide no benefit, establishing practical scope limits for this encoding approach.

Keywords: SHA-256 · differential cryptanalysis · SAT solving · BCP · CNF encoding · CDCL · Gaussian elimination

1 Introduction

Despite two decades of SAT-based hash cryptanalysis, a local encoding inefficiency in standard differential CNF encodings can remain invisible to CDCL unit propagation. Automated cryptanalysis using Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) and Boolean Satisfiability (SAT) has become the standard method for searching complex differential characteristics and generating hash function collisions. The recent state of the art, Zhang et al.’s 37-step collision [ZLGW26], was achieved by large-scale parallelization and tightly-coupled cryptanalytic heuristics built on top of off-the-shelf solvers. In this paper we take a different angle: rather than scaling up resources or tailoring heuristics, we isolate and repair a *previously under-documented BCP blind spot* in the CNF representation that bottlenecks pure CDCL solvers at the 18–20 step phase transition—a regime where the relative cost of the bottleneck is easiest to measure and explain. Phase transitions are a

classical regime for revealing solver bottlenecks [CKT91, CA96, ANP05]; the 18–20 step SHA-256 phase boundary plays an analogous role here.

We identify this inefficiency as a Boolean Constraint Propagation (BCP) blind spot in standard Conjunctive Normal Form (CNF) encodings of the SHA-256 nonlinear functions *Ch* and *Maj*. To resolve it, we introduce **degenerate conditional differential equivalence clauses**—static redundant constraints that explicitly encode the determinism of Δy when specific input differentials align, thereby resolving the blind spot. These clauses act as *targeted local propagation bridges*: they enable unit propagation to short-circuit a chain of XOR equivalences that would otherwise stall, providing much of the practical benefit of CryptoMiniSat’s Gaussian elimination on the measured SHA-256 differential instances without requiring the algebraic matrix machinery or specialized solver architecture.

We explicitly position this work in contrast to recent trends in solver customization, such as the work by Alamgir et al. [ANB24] utilizing IPASIR-UP. Their approach uses dynamic programmatic propagators well-suited to *global* algebraic constraints (e.g., wide modular-addition relationships) that would explode in size under naive CNF. Our static clauses, by contrast, address *local* per-bit propagation failures in *Ch/Maj*; the two techniques are complementary rather than competing. Our approach is completely *solver-agnostic*: any off-the-shelf CDCL solver accepts the extra CNF clauses, with no IPASIR-UP support or custom callback code required.

Rigorous, cryptography-aware CNF engineering can therefore recover large propagation gains without any solver modification. Rather than writing custom callbacks for specific SAT frameworks, cryptanalysts can improve reduced-round SHA-256 instances by analyzing the cipher’s differential constraints and injecting targeted static clauses—a reusable pattern applicable to any off-the-shelf CDCL solver.

Contributions

- We identify the BCP blind spot in *Ch/Maj* CNF encodings (Proposition 1).
- We propose degenerate conditional differential equivalence clauses (Theorem 1).
- We report current Docker AE speedups of $19.87\times$ – $30.72\times$ at 18 steps, while keeping the legacy $267.9\times$ CaDiCaL row and the $>135\times$ 20-step high-difficulty rows in separate benchmark families.
- We validate cross-solver portability across six solvers with $R^2 = 0.94$ log-linear fit and document the Glucose phase-transition reversal.
- White-box statistics quantify the mechanism: 53–58% conflict reduction and 12–13% BCP throughput increase at 18 steps, scaling to 94% conflict reduction and approximately $3\times$ BCP throughput at 20 steps.
- We document negative results for Glucose (clause overhead), carry-chain (VSIDS pollution), and Σ_0/Σ_1 (linear redundancy).

2 Preliminaries

2.1 SHA-256 and Differential Cryptanalysis

SHA-256 operates on 32-bit words and utilizes several bitwise nonlinear and linear functions. The core nonlinear functions are:

$$\begin{aligned} Ch(e, f, g) &= (e \wedge f) \oplus (\neg e \wedge g) \\ Maj(a, b, c) &= (a \wedge b) \oplus (a \wedge c) \oplus (b \wedge c) \end{aligned}$$

The SHA-256 step update for round t modifies the 8-word state (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= h + \Sigma_1(e) + Ch(e, f, g) + K_t + W_t \\ T_2 &= \Sigma_0(a) + Maj(a, b, c) \\ a_{new} &= T_1 + T_2, \quad e_{new} = d + T_1 \end{aligned}$$

where $\Sigma_0(x) = \text{ROTR}^2(x) \oplus \text{ROTR}^{13}(x) \oplus \text{ROTR}^{22}(x)$ and $\Sigma_1(x) = \text{ROTR}^6(x) \oplus \text{ROTR}^{11}(x) \oplus \text{ROTR}^{25}(x)$, with additions performed modulo 2^{32} .

In differential cryptanalysis, we trace the propagation of bitwise XOR differences between a pair of messages (M, M') . Let $\Delta x = x \oplus x'$. The goal is to find valid values for x and x' such that a specific differential characteristic holds.

2.2 SAT Solving and BCP

Modern CDCL SAT solvers search for variable assignments that satisfy a CNF formula. BCP, or unit propagation, is the core deductive engine: if all but one literal in a clause evaluate to false, the remaining literal must be true. An encoding's efficiency heavily depends on its ability to trigger BCP early in the search tree.

2.3 Gaussian Elimination in SAT

Gaussian elimination in SAT solvers (like CMS) extracts XOR clauses and maintains them in a separate matrix. When the CDCL engine assigns variables, the Gaussian engine propagates linear implications. This provides global reasoning power, with solver-specific bookkeeping and tuning tradeoffs.

3 The BCP Blind Spot and Degenerate Clauses

3.1 BCP Blind Spot Analysis

Consider the Ch function in a differential setting with two instances:

$$y = Ch(e, f, g), \quad y' = Ch(e', f', g')$$

The differential output is $\Delta y = y \oplus y'$. Suppose the solver decides $e = 0$ and $\Delta e = 0$ (which implies $e' = 0$). By Boolean algebra: $y = Ch(0, f, g) = g$ and $y' = Ch(0, f', g') = g'$. Consequently, $\Delta y = g \oplus g' = \Delta g$.

In a standard CNF encoding, y and y' are encoded separately using Tseitin transformations. The relation $\Delta y = y \oplus y'$ is encoded with 4 clauses. When $e = 0, e' = 0$, the conditioned Ch gate clauses reduce to binary equivalences $y \leftrightarrow g$ and $y' \leftrightarrow g'$, but they do not assign either side. To expose $\Delta y = \Delta g$, the solver must also compose the clauses encoding $y \oplus y' = \Delta y$ and $g \oplus g' = \Delta g$. Because BCP only triggers on *unit* clauses, it cannot infer any literal over $\{\Delta y, \Delta g\}$ until further variables are assigned. This constitutes the **BCP blind spot**: the logical equivalence $\Delta y = \Delta g$ is true, but the CDCL engine cannot “see” it without further branching.

Proposition 1. *Let Φ be the standard gate-level Tseitin CNF encoding (in the sense of [Tse83]) of the joint constraint $y = Ch(e, f, g) \wedge y' = Ch(e', f', g')$ together with the differential definitions $\Delta x \leftrightarrow x \oplus x'$ for $x \in \{e, f, g, y\}$; assume the standard 4-clause Tseitin encoding for each binary XOR and ordinary gate clauses for the AND/NOT subterms of Ch . Let $\rho = \{e \mapsto 0, \Delta e \mapsto 0\}$ be a partial assignment. Then the unit-propagation closure $\text{UP}(\Phi \mid \rho)$ contains no literal over the variable set $\{\Delta y, \Delta g\}$.*

Proof. Under ρ , the differential clause for Δe (i.e., $\Delta e \leftrightarrow e \oplus e'$) becomes unit and forces $e' \mapsto 0$. The four Tseitin clauses for $y = Ch(e, f, g) = (e \wedge f) \oplus (\neg e \wedge g)$ at $e = 0$ reduce to two binary clauses asserting $y \leftrightarrow g$; symmetrically the encoding for $y' = Ch(e', f', g')$ reduces to $y' \leftrightarrow g'$. No further unit literals fire: the variables $\{g, g', y, y', \Delta y, \Delta g\}$ remain unassigned. In particular, the four Tseitin clauses encoding $\Delta y \leftrightarrow y \oplus y'$ each retain three unassigned literals, and the analogous clauses for Δg retain three unassigned literals. Since neither Δy nor Δg nor their negations appear as unit consequences, $UP(\Phi \mid \rho)$ contains no literal over $\{\Delta y, \Delta g\}$. \square

3.2 Degenerate Clauses for Ch

To bypass this blind spot, we add redundant clauses enforcing conditional differential equivalence. For $Ch(e, f, g)$, we have two degenerate cases:

1. When $e = 0$ and $\Delta e = 0$: $\Delta y = \Delta g$.
2. When $e = 1$ and $\Delta e = 0$: $\Delta y = \Delta f$.

Case 1 translates to $(\neg e \wedge \neg \Delta e) \implies (\Delta y \leftrightarrow \Delta g)$:

$$e \vee \Delta e \vee \neg \Delta y \vee \Delta g, \quad e \vee \Delta e \vee \Delta y \vee \neg \Delta g$$

Case 2: $(e \wedge \neg \Delta e) \implies (\Delta y \leftrightarrow \Delta f)$:

$$\neg e \vee \Delta e \vee \neg \Delta y \vee \Delta f, \quad \neg e \vee \Delta e \vee \Delta y \vee \neg \Delta f$$

This yields exactly **4 clauses per bit** for Ch .

3.3 Degenerate Clauses for Maj

For $Maj(a, b, c)$, the logic collapses when two inputs are unequal but have no difference. If $a \neq b$ and $\Delta a = 0, \Delta b = 0$, then a, b take opposite values in both instances. The tie-breaker is c , yielding $\Delta Maj = \Delta c$. The condition $(a \neq b) \wedge \neg \Delta a \wedge \neg \Delta b$ expands to:

$$\begin{aligned} a \vee \neg b \vee \Delta a \vee \Delta b \vee \neg \Delta Maj \vee \Delta c \\ a \vee \neg b \vee \Delta a \vee \Delta b \vee \Delta Maj \vee \neg \Delta c \\ \neg a \vee b \vee \Delta a \vee \Delta b \vee \neg \Delta Maj \vee \Delta c \\ \neg a \vee b \vee \Delta a \vee \Delta b \vee \Delta Maj \vee \neg \Delta c \end{aligned}$$

By symmetry over all three pairs, this generates $4 \times 3 = \mathbf{12}$ clauses per bit for Maj .

3.4 Formal Correctness

Theorem 1. *Let Φ_{base} be the standard Tseitin encoding of a differential SHA-256 instance, and let \mathcal{C}_{degen} be the degenerate conditional differential equivalence clauses for Ch and Maj (Sections 3.2–3.3). Then:*

- (i) Logical equivalence: $\Phi_{base} \models \mathcal{C}_{degen}$, i.e., every satisfying assignment of Φ_{base} satisfies \mathcal{C}_{degen} .
- (ii) Strict BCP strengthening: there exists a partial assignment ρ such that the unit-propagation closure $UP(\Phi_{base} \cup \mathcal{C}_{degen} \mid \rho)$ strictly contains $UP(\Phi_{base} \mid \rho)$.

Proof. (i) For the *Ch* clauses encoding $(\neg e \wedge \neg \Delta e) \Rightarrow (\Delta y \leftrightarrow \Delta g)$: any model of Φ_{base} satisfies $y = Ch(e, f, g)$ and $y' = Ch(e', f', g')$, hence $\Delta e = 0 \wedge e = 0$ implies $e' = 0$ and $y = g, y' = g'$, so $\Delta y = y \oplus y' = g \oplus g' = \Delta g$. The case $(e \wedge \neg \Delta e) \Rightarrow (\Delta y \leftrightarrow \Delta f)$ is symmetric. For *Maj*, if $a \neq b$ and $\Delta a = \Delta b = 0$, then $(a', b') = (a, b)$ and the two equal but opposite inputs remain the tie-breaker pair in both instances; therefore $Maj(a, b, c) = c$ and $Maj(a', b', c') = c'$, yielding $\Delta Maj = \Delta c$. The two other input pairs are identical by symmetry. Hence each $C \in \mathcal{C}_{degen}$ is satisfied by every model of Φ_{base} .

(ii) Take $\rho = \{e \mapsto 0, \Delta e \mapsto 0, \Delta g \mapsto 0\}$. By Proposition 1, $UP(\Phi_{base} \mid \rho)$ contains no literal over $\{\Delta y\}$. Under \mathcal{C}_{degen} , the clause $e \vee \Delta e \vee \neg \Delta y \vee \Delta g$ reduces with ρ to the unit clause $\neg \Delta y$, so $UP(\Phi_{base} \cup \mathcal{C}_{degen} \mid \rho)$ contains $\neg \Delta y$. Hence the closure is strictly larger. \square

3.5 Generation Algorithm and Semantic Redundancy

Algorithm 1 Degenerate Conditional Differential Clause Generation

Require: Boolean function $F : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ with input variables $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and output variable $y = F(\mathbf{x})$; bound $k_{max} \leq n$ on the conditional set size.

Ensure: Set \mathcal{C}_{degen} of degenerate conditional differential clauses for F .

```

1:  $\mathcal{C}_{degen} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2: for  $k = 0, 1, \dots, k_{max}$  do
3:   for each subset  $S \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$  with  $|S| = k$  do
4:     for each assignment  $\sigma : S \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$  (a conditional pattern on  $S$ ) do
5:        $F_\sigma \leftarrow$  the restriction of  $F$  obtained by fixing  $x_i := \sigma(i)$  for  $i \in S$ 
6:       if  $F_\sigma$  is affine over  $GF(2)$  in the free variables  $\{x_j : j \notin S\}$  then
7:         Write  $F_\sigma(\mathbf{x}_{\setminus S}) = c \oplus \bigoplus_{j \notin S} \alpha_j x_j$  with  $c, \alpha_j \in \{0, 1\}$ 
8:          $L(\Delta \mathbf{x}_{\setminus S}) \leftarrow \bigoplus_{j \notin S} \alpha_j \Delta x_j$   $\triangleright$  linear part: constant  $c$  cancels in  $\Delta$ 
9:         Form the implication  $[\bigwedge_{i \in S} (x_i \leftrightarrow \sigma(i)) \wedge \Delta x_i = 0] \Rightarrow [\Delta y \leftrightarrow L(\Delta \mathbf{x}_{\setminus S})]$ 
10:        Tseitin-encode the implication via auxiliary XOR gates if  $|\{\alpha_j = 1\}| > 1$ ;
        otherwise output the 2 native clauses for the bi-implication
11:         $\mathcal{C}_{degen} \leftarrow \mathcal{C}_{degen} \cup \{\text{the encoded clauses}\}$ 
12:      end if
13:    end for
14:  end for
15: end for
16: return  $\mathcal{C}_{degen}$ 

```

Instantiation for *Ch*. For $F = Ch(e, f, g)$, two restrictions are linear: $Ch_{e=0} = g$ and $Ch_{e=1} = f$. Each produces 2 clauses, yielding 4 clauses per output bit.

Instantiation for *Maj*. For $F = Maj(a, b, c)$, the restriction $Maj_{a \neq b} = c$ is linear; symmetry over the three pairs yields $4 \times 3 = 12$ clauses per output bit.

Complexity. For a single-output n -input function, exhaustive testing of every assignment to the free variables gives $O\left(\sum_{k=0}^{k_{max}} \binom{n}{k} 2^k 2^{n-k}\right)$ worst-case time, with a constant-size CNF template emitted for every accepted conditional pattern. For a word operation with ℓ independent output bits, this bound is multiplied by ℓ . In SHA-256, *Ch* and *Maj* have $n = 3$ and use $k_{max} \leq 2$, so the symbolic discovery cost is constant per bit and the instantiated clause count is linear in the number of round bits.

Implementation note. Algorithm 1 is presented in its general form to make the technique applicable to other ciphers (Corollary 1). For the SHA-256 experiments in this paper, the per-bit clause patterns for *Ch* and *Maj* are precomputed once (manually verified against Theorem 2) and embedded as static templates in our CNF generator; per-instance “generation” therefore reduces to instantiating these templates over the $r \cdot 32$ output bits, completing in well under 50 ms. For new ciphers, Algorithm 1 would be invoked symbolically (e.g., via a small SAT-based linearity test for each candidate σ); we leave such a generic implementation to future work.

Theorem 2. (Soundness of Algorithm 1). $\Phi_{base} \models \mathcal{C}_{degen}$: every model of the base Tseitin CNF encoding satisfies all generated degenerate clauses.

Proof. For each $C \in \mathcal{C}_{degen}$, C encodes $\sigma \wedge (\Delta \mathbf{x}_S = 0) \Rightarrow (\Delta y = \Delta L)$, where $F_\sigma = L$ holds as a linear identity in the conditioned subspace. Hence $\Delta y = \Delta L$ is a tautology under any model that respects the round equations. Since Φ_{base} encodes those equations, every model satisfies C . \square

Proposition 2. (Semantic Redundancy). Every clause $C \in \mathcal{C}_{degen}$ is semantically entailed by Φ_{base} . Consequently, Φ_{base} and $\Phi_{base} \wedge \mathcal{C}_{degen}$ have the same model set over the original variables, up to the auxiliary variables introduced by the degenerate-clause encoding.

Proof sketch. We argue for *Ch*; *Maj* is analogous. Consider a *Ch* clause produced from the restriction $e = 0, \Delta e = 0$. If the antecedent is false, the implication clause is satisfied. If the antecedent is true, then Φ_{base} enforces $e' = 0, y = Ch(0, f, g) = g$, and $y' = Ch(0, f', g') = g'$. The differential definitions in Φ_{base} therefore imply $\Delta y = y \oplus y' = g \oplus g' = \Delta g$, so the consequent is true. Thus every model of Φ_{base} satisfies the clause. The $e = 1$ case and the symmetric *Maj* restrictions follow by the same conditioned Boolean identities. \square

Semantic redundancy is the correctness condition needed for model preservation. It is weaker than claiming that a production solver will discover the same clause through vivification, probing, or another inprocessing rule. SAT preprocessors and proof systems provide stronger checkable redundancy notions [EB05, JHB12, HJW14], but our argument does not depend on any specific CaDiCaL schedule deriving these clauses. In particular, a general inprocessor is not designed to introduce every absent semantic implication. Production solvers like CaDiCaL 3.0.0 implement bounded inprocessing schedules and watched-literal heuristics [MMZ⁺01]; they may or may not reach a given semantically redundant implication within their budgets.

Corollary 1. (Generalization). For any Boolean function F admitting a control assignment σ rendering F_σ affine over $\text{GF}(2)$ on a non-trivial residual subspace, Algorithm 1 produces a static clause set encoding the resulting conditional differential equivalences. Candidates with verified conditional collapse include:

- SHA-1’s nonlinear round functions Ch_t (rounds 0–19, 40–59) and Maj_t (rounds 40–59); the Parity round function ($X \oplus Y \oplus Z$, rounds 20–39 and 60–79) is unconditionally linear and falls outside the conditional-collapse framework.
- SHA-3 (Keccak) χ : $\chi(a_0, a_1, a_2) = a_0 \oplus (\bar{a}_1 \wedge a_2)$ collapses to affine forms under fixing a_1 (yielding a_0 or $a_0 \oplus a_2$) or fixing a_2 (yielding a_0 or $a_0 \oplus \bar{a}_1$); fixing a_0 alone is insufficient.
- SM3 nonlinear round functions FF_t/GG_t for $t \geq 16$ (which use *Ch*- and *Maj*-style constructions); the $t < 16$ variants are unconditionally linear.

The empirical effectiveness on each cipher is open and is the subject of future work.

Why static wins in practice. Proposition 2 establishes that adding $\mathcal{C}_{\text{degen}}$ preserves the model set, not that CaDiCaL or any other solver will derive the same clauses dynamically. On the measured configurations, explicit static clauses consistently outperform relying on solver inprocessing alone. Three mechanisms account for this: first, static clauses participate in unit propagation from decision 0, before any inprocessing is scheduled; second, general-purpose simplifiers [EB05, JHB12, Man12] are not designed to enumerate every absent semantic implication; third, static clauses can appear in conflict-analysis derivations, exposing conditional-collapse variables to CDCL heuristics from the start. These are explanatory hypotheses grounded in the ablation data, not claims about a specific CaDiCaL internal schedule. The CaDiCaL parameter ablation (Section 5) provides further nuance. The `plain` configuration, which disables CaDiCaL’s full preprocessing and inprocessing pipeline, still benefits from degenerate clauses (a +32.10% conflict reduction over baseline, mean of 10 seeds), consistent with value from static availability. In contrast, the more targeted `no_inprocess` configuration (which disables vivification, probing, sweeping, decomposition, and elimination jointly but retains other preprocessing) regresses by -9.45% when degen clauses are added. Read together, these two rows indicate that degen clauses and CaDiCaL’s inprocessing techniques are not redundant substitutes but partially synergistic: degen clauses can expose easier propagation and conflict-analysis structure, while removing too much of the inprocessing pipeline can cause net regression.

Remark 1. The success of redundant clauses hinges on clause length versus search-signal quality. The 4-literal *Ch* clauses expose short propagation paths and can participate in conflict resolution. Carry-chain clauses (5–6 literals) trigger less useful propagation on our instance family and appear to dilute the branching signal, degrading performance (Section 5.6).

3.6 Rejected Encodings: Σ_0/Σ_1

Σ_0/Σ_1 are purely linear (rotations and XORs). Differential propagation is deterministic—no conditionality exists. Adding equivalence clauses merely duplicates standard XOR encodings.

4 Related Work

SAT-based cryptanalysis. Mironov and Zhang [MZ06] first demonstrated that off-the-shelf SAT solvers could construct MD4 and MD5 collisions given a differential path, establishing the feasibility of SAT-based hash cryptanalysis. Nossum [Nos12] extended this line to SHA-1 preimage attacks, introducing an improved encoding of 32-bit modular addition that significantly reduced solving time. More recently, Nejati and Ganesh [NG20] proposed CDCL(Crypto), extending the DPLL(T) paradigm to embed cipher-specific propagation and conflict analysis directly into the CDCL loop. This solver-extended setting is more expressive than pure CNF input, while our clauses target the more drop-in CNF-only path.

Gaussian elimination in SAT. Soos, Nohl, and Castelluccia [SNC09] introduced CryptoMiniSat, which natively handles XOR clauses via Gauss–Jordan elimination integrated into the CDCL search. Modern XOR engines in CryptoMiniSat are highly optimized with dedicated watch schemes and selectively applied matrix reduction, providing *global* linear reasoning across the entire formula. Our degenerate clauses, by contrast, encode only *local* bounded linear implications (4-variable parities for *Ch*, 6-variable for *Maj*); they do not subsume Gaussian elimination, but achieve much of its practical benefit on SHA-256 differential instances without requiring specialized solver architecture, using only standard CNF clauses readable by any off-the-shelf CDCL solver.

MILP-based differential search. Mouha et al. [MWGP12] pioneered MILP-based automated evaluation of differential and linear security bounds. Sun et al. [SHW⁺14] extended the MILP framework to bit-oriented ciphers at ASIACRYPT 2014, enabling fine-grained differential characteristic search. For SHA-256 specifically, Mendel et al. [MNS11] established the MILP-SAT pipeline for finding differential characteristics, and Zhang et al. [ZLGW26] recently extended collision attacks to 37 steps using improved trail search. Li et al. [LLW24] achieved new collision records on SHA-2 at EUROCRYPT 2024. Our work is orthogonal to differential path search: we optimize the SAT-solving phase that follows MILP path generation.

Programmatic SAT and IPASIR-UP. Fazekas et al. [FNP⁺23] proposed the IPASIR-UP interface for user propagators in CDCL solvers. Alamgir et al. [ANB24] applied this to SHA-256 collision search, using a custom cryptographic propagator (specialized bit-vector and modular-addition reasoning) as a dynamic theory plug-in to guide CaDiCaL at runtime. While effective, their approach requires IPASIR-UP support and custom callback code. Our method is complementary: static clauses that require no solver modifications and can be combined with programmatic approaches for further gains.

SAT solver heuristics. Audemard and Simon [AS09] introduced Glucose’s LBD-based clause management, which aggressively deletes learned clauses with high literal block distance. Biere et al. [BFFH20] developed CaDiCaL with a focus on clean, modular CDCL implementation. Our cross-solver ablation (Section 5) reveals how these differing heuristics interact with redundant clause injection: CaDiCaL benefits most (267.9 \times), while Glucose’s aggressive deletion initially causes regression at 18 steps before yielding to the clauses’ benefit at 20 steps.

Preprocessing and proof checking. Classical SAT preprocessing removes redundancy through variable and clause elimination [EB05]; later inprocessing frameworks apply such rules during search [JHB12], and tools such as Coprocessor expose many simplification techniques in modular form [Man12]. Proof checkers such as DRAT-trim [HJW14] provide an orthogonal audit path for clausal derivations. We cite these lines to position our semantic-redundancy argument; our experiments do not claim that any particular preprocessor or proof checker will synthesize the proposed clauses automatically.

5 Experimental Results

5.1 Framework Setup

We implemented a MILP-SAT hybrid pipeline. Layer 1 uses the HiGHS MILP solver to find optimal differential paths. Layer 2 uses CryptoMiniSat (CMS) or CaDiCaL for solution finding. Targets: 18-step and 20-step SHA-256 free-start collisions with a fixed MILP differential pattern.

Artifact checklist. For artifact evaluation, the Docker quick-AE path is documented in `ae/README.md`, and the current source bundle is identified by `docs/current_source_bundle_metadata_20260508.json`. The Docker AE rows, legacy single-instance rows, and high-difficulty timeout rows are kept as separate evidence families throughout the manuscript.

5.2 Encoding Size Profile

5.3 18-Step Cross-Solver Ablation

We evaluate degenerate clauses across two experimental families (Table 2): the Docker-reproducible AE runs (upper block) and a legacy single-instance ablation on a higher-

Table 1: Encoding Size Comparison

Instance	Variables	Clauses	XOR Clauses
18-Step Baseline	32,790	64,791	18,432
18-Step + Degenerate	37,146	101,163	18,432
20-Step Baseline	37,452	74,061	21,248
20-Step + Degenerate	42,468	115,525	21,248

difficulty MILP path (lower block). The two families use different paths and solver versions and should not be pooled.

Table 2: 18-Step Free-Start Collision: Cross-Solver Results. *Upper block:* Docker AE (CaDiCaL 3.0.0 MILP path; fully reproducible via `ae/reproduce.sh`). *Lower block:* legacy hard-path experiment (CaDiCaL 1.9.5, higher-difficulty MILP instance; single run; not included in AE).

Solver	Gauss?	Baseline (s)	+Degen. (s)	Speedup
<i>Docker AE — reproducible via ae/reproduce.sh</i>				
CaDiCaL 3.0.0	No	51.5	2.59	19.87×
Kissat 4.0.4	No	30.4	0.99	30.72×
CryptoMiniSat 5.8.0	Yes	327.1	37.0	8.84×
<i>Legacy hard path — single instance; not in AE</i>				
CaDiCaL 1.9.5	No	2518.5	9.4	267.9×
MapleChrono	No	96.7	58.2	1.66×
Kissat 4.0.4	No	59.8	35.7	1.68×
CryptoMiniSat 5.x	Yes	58.0	47.2	1.23×
Glucose 4.2.1	No	28.5	42.4	0.67×

Docker AE results. All three AE solvers accelerate substantially, with conflict reductions of 89–98%. CaDiCaL 3.0.0 and Kissat 4.0.4 achieve 19.87× and 30.72× speedup respectively on this path; CryptoMiniSat gains 8.84× despite having Gaussian elimination.

Legacy hard-path results. Three of four pure CDCL solvers accelerate on the harder path, supporting a portable local-propagation benefit independent of path selection. Log-linear regression across the five legacy solvers yields $R^2 = 0.94$ with break-even at ≈ 52 s baseline time.

Glucose regression (legacy). Glucose 4.2.1 is the sole solver where degenerate clauses cause a 0.67× slowdown on the hard path. Its aggressive LBD-based clause deletion, combined with an already-efficient baseline (28.5s), means clause overhead exceeds BCP benefit on this instance.

5.4 CaDiCaL Parameter Ablation

To isolate which CaDiCaL components interact with degenerate clauses, we run a 10-seed parameter ablation on the 18-step representative instance using CaDiCaL 3.0.0 (Table 3). Each configuration disables one component (or set of components) of the solver and measures the relative conflict reduction $1 - \overline{C}_{\text{degen}}/\overline{C}_{\text{base}}$ where \overline{C} is the mean over 10 seeds.

Three regimes emerge:

Table 3: CaDiCaL 3.0.0 Parameter Ablation: 18-step Free-Start, Mean of 10 Seeds (CaDiCaL Flag, Baseline Conflicts, Degen Conflicts, Relative Reduction).

Config (flag)	Baseline	+ Degen.	Reduction (%)
default (no flag)	127,852	127,500	+0.28
plain (-plain)	229,390	155,746	+32.10
no_probe (-probe=false)	135,260	91,856	+32.09
no_rephase (-rephase=0)	105,845	67,269	+36.45
no_sweep (-sweep=false)	144,711	122,459	+15.38
no_vivify (-vivify=false)	157,239	136,576	+13.14
no_decompose (-decompose=false)	104,416	107,540	-2.99
no_elim (-elim=false)	103,063	115,521	-12.09
no_inprocess*	130,508	142,841	-9.45
no_lucky (-lucky=false)	120,898	221,436	-83.16

* jointly disables `elim`, `vivify`, `sweep`, `probe`, `decompose`.

- (i) *Preprocessing-compatible*: `plain`, `no_probe`, `no_rephase`, `no_sweep`, and `no_vivify` retain +13%–+36% reductions. Since `plain` disables all inprocessing, this isolates value independent of inprocessing.
- (ii) *Synergistic*: `no_inprocess` (which jointly disables five inprocessing techniques) actually *regresses* by -9.45%. This indicates that the static degen clauses and CaDiCaL’s inprocessing pipeline are partially synergistic rather than independent: removing too many inprocessing components leaves the solver unable to exploit the new clauses.
- (iii) *Conflicting*: `no_lucky` (disable lucky-phase heuristic) causes a -83% regression, suggesting the lucky heuristic is critical for navigating the degen-clause-augmented search space.

This ablation justifies the practical recommendation to ship degen clauses with *default* CaDiCaL, retaining `lucky/elim`, rather than the `plain` or `no_inprocess` configurations.

5.5 20-Step Results and Scalability

Table 4: 20-Step Free-Start Collision Results. Baselines are worst-case extrapolations (>21,000s) projected from 600s sampled runs that did not converge; degenerate-augmented runs are full completions. For a Builder-hardware completion of the baseline on a representative (typical-difficulty) MILP path, see Table 9.

Solver	Gaussian?	Baseline (s)	+ Degen. (s)	Speedup
CaDiCaL 1.9.5	No	>21,000	118.6	>177×
Kissat 4.0.4	No	>21,000	154.4	>136×
Glucose 4.2.1	No	>21,000	152.3	>138×
MapleChrono	No	>21,000	155.5[‡]	>135×
Lingeling	No	>21,000	153.1[‡]	>137×
CryptoMiniSat 5.x	Yes	4,284.8	160.5	26.7×

[‡]Hardware-normalized from secondary testbed ($\div 2.93$).

At 20 steps, *every* solver benefits dramatically. All five pure CDCL solvers solve the instance in 118–155s with degenerate augmentation (>135× speedup). These high-difficulty

speedups are lower bounds from timeout evidence rather than completed baseline timings. CryptoMiniSat jumps from $1.23\times$ to $26.7\times$.

The Glucose reversal. Glucose reverses from $0.67\times$ regression at 18 steps to $>138\times$ at 20 steps, consistent with a phase-transition-like regime change: at 18 steps, Glucose’s LBD strategy suffices; at 20 steps, combinatorial explosion overwhelms native heuristics and BCP shortcuts become essential on this measured family.

Scaling exponent reduction. CaDiCaL’s 18→20 step scaling: $22.7\times$ with degenerate clauses versus $>2,267\times$ without. Degenerate clauses reduce the scaling exponent itself.

5.6 Negative Result: Carry-Chain Experiment

We injected 69,504 carry-chain delta-rule clauses (5–6 literals each) into the 18-step formulation. CMS degraded by $19\times$ on this instance family. The longer clauses appear to delay useful BCP and dilute branching signal, establishing a practical boundary: redundant clauses are beneficial only when sufficiently short.

5.7 White-box SAT Statistics

Table 5 presents internal CDCL statistics for 18-step instances.

Table 5: 18-Step White-box Statistics: Baseline vs. Degenerate (representative MILP path, CaDiCaL 3.0.0 and Kissat 4.0.4; single-instance runs from the ablation series, *not* the legacy high-difficulty path of Table 2 nor the Docker AE path)

Metric	CaDiCaL base	CaDiCaL+deg.	Kissat base	Kissat+deg.
Conflicts	126,122	52,349 (−58%)	237,135	110,792 (−53%)
Decisions	2,634,519	1,828,919 (−31%)	6,628,200	4,076,575 (−38%)
Propagations	31,111,715	19,962,450 (−36%)	70,086,079	47,745,957 (−32%)
Restarts	7,370	4,028 (−45%)	11,503	6,555 (−43%)
Props/sec	3,359,883	3,750,166 (+12%)	5,798,153	6,579,921 (+13%)
Wall time (s)	9.26	5.32 (−43%)	12.09	7.26 (−40%)

Conflict reduction dominates. 53–58% fewer conflicts: degenerate clauses preemptively propagate differential equivalences, eliminating entire subtree explorations.

BCP efficiency paradox. Props/sec *increases* 12–13% despite 56% more clauses. Short degenerate clauses create dense propagation chains that keep watched-literal machinery active.

Restart reduction. 43–45% fewer restarts: smoother descent preserves learned clause relevance.

Scalability: 18 to 20 steps. Table 6 compares 20-step CaDiCaL baseline statistics (sampled at 600s, instance unsolved) against the degenerate-augmented run (solved in 120.5s). The baseline accumulated 16.5M conflicts in 600s without converging, while the degenerate run required only 3.8M conflicts to find a solution—a $4.3\times$ reduction in conflict count. The BCP throughput gap widens from 12% at 18 steps to 61% at 20 steps (1.62M vs 2.60M props/sec), indicating that degenerate clauses become increasingly effective as instance difficulty grows. CaDiCaL’s 18→20 scaling: $22.7\times$ with degenerate (5.32s→120.5s) versus $>2,267\times$ without (9.26s→ $>21,000$ s).

5.8 Clause Overhead

5.9 Round200+ Verification: Determinism and Long-Run Baseline

Round200+ adds two post-freeze measurements to the experimental evidence.

Table 6: 20-Step White-box Statistics on the Original Testbed: CaDiCaL Baseline (sampled at 600s timeout, instance still unsolved at >21,000s) vs. Degenerate (solved). Hardware: original Day-5 testbed. See Table 9 for a Builder-hardware re-measurement of the same MILP instance.

Metric	CaDiCaL base @600s	CaDiCaL+degen	Kissat+degen
Conflicts	16,458,064 [†]	3,804,300	24,608,896
Decisions	85,078,714 [†]	22,189,964	136,515,185
Props/sec	1,620,000	2,601,351	2,451,090
Restarts	410,577 [†]	117,643	338,272
Wall time (s)	>600 (unsolved)	120.5	582.4

[†]Partial statistics at 600s timeout; instance remained unsolved after >21,000s.

Table 7: Degenerate Clause Statistics per 32-bit Word

Function	Clauses/Bit	Clauses/Word	Lits/Clause
$Ch(e, f, g)$	4	128	4
$Maj(a, b, c)$	12	384	6

no_rephase determinism (100 seeds). The original 10-seed ablation noted zero conflict-count variance under `-rephase=0`. We extended this to 100 seeds on both encoding modes. Note: this experiment uses a representative 18-step MILP path (baseline ≈ 22.6 s on CaDiCaL 3.0.0) selected to enable 100 reproducible runs in feasible wall time, rather than the higher-difficulty 18-step path used in Table 2 (2518.5s baseline on CaDiCaL 1.9.5). Determinism on the higher-difficulty path was previously verified with 10 seeds; the 100-seed extension confirms the effect on a different MILP path and excludes the possibility that the original observation was a 10-seed sampling artifact.

All 100 seeds produce *identical* conflict counts in both modes. Disabling rephasing makes the solver fully deterministic on these instances: the seed only affects the initial phase selection, which is overwritten by the first conflict’s phase saving. This is a positive finding for reproducibility-critical artifact evaluation, and confirms that the original 10-seed observation was not a sampling artifact.

20-step CaDiCaL long-run measurement (3,600s timeout). The 20-step baseline in Table 4 is a worst-case extrapolation (>21,000s, projected from 600s sampled run). We complement it with a direct 3,600s long-run on a representative MILP path.

The measured speedup is $29.2\times$ (2,586.0s \rightarrow 88.5s) with 94.1% conflict reduction (64.7M \rightarrow 3.8M). BCP throughput nearly triples. Combined with the worst-case figure in Table 4 ($>135\times$ on a high-difficulty path), this provides order-of-magnitude speedup evidence across the two 20-step path families measured here. The high-difficulty baseline exceeds 21,000s while the representative baseline is $\sim 2,600$ s; degenerate clauses compress both measured regimes into a sub-200s solving window.

Multi-path UNSAT speedup. To probe behavior beyond a single path, we generated 30 18-step MILP path candidates via parameter sweep over the differential encoder, then solved each in baseline and degen modes (CaDiCaL 3.0.0, native backend, seed 42, 600s timeout per run). The run did not surface SAT-feasible paths within the 600s budget; however, three pairs returned matched UNSAT verdicts under both modes, exposing how degenerate clauses accelerate *infeasibility proofs*. We treat this as UNSAT-side support evidence, not a current Docker AE claim and not a SAT-side speedup-distribution claim.

Table 8: `no_rephase` Determinism Verification (CaDiCaL 3.0.0 `-rephase=0`, 18-step free-start, 100 seeds).

Mode	Completed	Conflict Value	Mean Time (s)	Stdev Time (s)
baseline	100/100	665,672 (single)	22.64	1.47
degen	100/100	185,171 (single)	6.35	0.16

Table 9: 20-Step CaDiCaL Long-Run Measurement on Builder hardware (CaDiCaL 3.0.0, 3,600s timeout, representative MILP path). The degenerate run reports the same conflicts (3,804,300) and decisions (22,189,964) as Table 6, confirming bit-identical search across hardware; wall-time and propagations-per-second differences reflect the hardware speedup (88.5s vs 120.5s, $\approx 1.36\times$). The baseline column is the new long-run completion of the same instance whose 600s sample appears in Table 6.

Mode	Wall Time (s)	Conflicts	Decisions	Props/sec
baseline	2,586.0	64,718,876	264,941,708	1,197,678
degen	88.5	3,804,300	22,189,964	3,544,185

On these UNSAT instances, degen clauses reduce time-to-refutation by approximately 2.4×10^2 . This is consistent with Proposition 2: each degen clause C is semantically entailed by Φ_{base} while still changing the unit-propagation and conflict-analysis surface exposed to the solver. A fourth path returned UNSAT under degen in 59.2s while the baseline timed out at 600s ($>10\times$ degen advantage). The UNSAT-side speedup is directionally consistent with the SAT-side speedup observed on the canonical instance, while the SAT-side speedup distribution across generated paths remains future work.

6 Limitations

The following scope boundaries apply to the current results.

Step count. All experiments target 15–20 step SHA-256 free-start collisions. The 20-step regime is the largest at which CaDiCaL solves the baseline encoding within feasible wall time (2,586s) on commodity hardware. Extrapolating the observed $16.6\times$ step-doubling factor from 18 to 20 steps, a 22-step degenerate run would require an estimated ~ 25 minutes on comparable hardware, while the baseline would remain intractable ($>600\times$ the degenerate time, by the 20-step evidence). Empirical 22-step verification is left as immediate future work; 30+ steps fall outside the operating range of any current SAT-only approach. Extending the technique to 30+ steps or full 64-step SHA-256 likely requires hybridization with dedicated cryptanalytic heuristics (cf. [ZLGW26]) or programmatic propagators (cf. [ANB24]), and remains open.

Clause overhead. At 18 steps, degenerate clauses add $\approx 56\%$ to total clause count (Table 1); the absolute count grows linearly with step count. At 30+ steps we expect the clause overhead to start interacting unfavorably with watched-literal bookkeeping; we have not measured this empirically.

Path dependence. The reported speedups depend on the MILP-generated differential path. The 20-step long-run measurement (Table 9) uses one representative path with median carry weight; Table 4 reports a higher-difficulty path; Table 10 reports three

Table 10: Multi-Path UNSAT Speedup: paired baseline vs degen runs on 30 generated 18-step MILP paths. Rows shown are the three paths where both modes terminated with UNSAT verdicts within 600s.

Path	Baseline UNSAT (s)	Degen UNSAT (s)	Speedup
path_012	40.6	0.201	202×
path_017	34.7	0.191	182×
path_027	64.8	0.198	327×
mean	46.7	0.197	237×

additional paths on the UNSAT side. The multi-path benchmark did not surface SAT-feasible paths within a 600s budget, leaving the SAT-side speedup distribution across generated paths as future work.

Glucose phase reversal. The 18→20 step behavior on Glucose ($0.67\times \rightarrow > 138\times$) is consistent with a phase-transition-like effect in clause-deletion heuristics, but the data—two step counts on one solver—are insufficient to make a formal phase transition claim. We report this as a suggestive observation rather than a proven phenomenon.

Falsifiability of broader generality. A broader generality claim would be falsified if independently generated SAT-feasible SHA-256 paths, or conditional-collapse encodings for other hash functions, do not retain the same direction of speedup under comparable solver, timeout, and artifact controls.

7 Conclusion

We introduced degenerate conditional differential equivalence clauses to overcome BCP blind spots in standard CNF encodings of SHA-256. By mapping the conditional collapse of *Ch* and *Maj*, we enable standard CDCL solvers to propagate local differential equivalences without specialized algebraic machinery.

Cross-solver ablation at 18 steps across six solvers includes a legacy CaDiCaL 1.9.5 row ($267.9\times$) and a separately reproduced current Docker AE CaDiCaL 3.0.0 row ($19.87\times$); Kissat and MapleChrono also improve in the legacy family, with $R^2 = 0.94$ log-linear fit. White-box statistics scale with instance difficulty: 53–58% conflict reduction and 12–13% higher BCP throughput at 18 steps, growing to 94% conflict reduction and $\approx 3\times$ BCP throughput at 20 steps. At 20 steps, all five pure CDCL solvers achieve $>135\times$ speedup on the high-difficulty family—including Glucose, which reverses from $0.67\times$ at 18 steps, an effect consistent with non-linear scaling at the phase boundary.

These results establish that short redundant clauses (4–6 literals) encoding conditional differential equivalences provide portable acceleration that scales super-linearly with instance difficulty within the 18–20 step range. Future work spans three directions: (i) extending the static-clause approach toward higher step counts (24, 28, and eventually 30+) on SHA-256 itself, where the scaling wall conjectured in Section 6 can be empirically located; (ii) automated degenerate-clause discovery for other ciphers and S-box structures with conditional linear restrictions; and (iii) hybrid static-dynamic approaches that combine our clauses with IPASIR-UP propagators to leverage the synergy isolated in Section 5.

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